

Teacher Job Satisfaction Among EFL Teachers in Higher Education in Japan

Bjorn FUISTING

『椋山女学園大学研究論集』第49号
人文科学篇（2018年3月）抜刷

Journal of Sugiyama Jogakuen University, No. 49 (Humanities) 2018
Sugiyama Jogakuen University, Nagoya, Japan

Teacher Job Satisfaction Among EFL Teachers in Higher Education in Japan

Bjorn FUISTING*

Abstract

Working conditions are rapidly changing within the educational sector in Japan. However, scarcely any research has been conducted on teacher job satisfaction among higher education EFL teachers in Japan, and none on how the implementation of the new employment rules affects job satisfaction among teachers on limited-term contracts. This paper outlines the recent changes in employment regulations and their impact on limited-term contracts and reports the findings from an investigation into teacher job satisfaction of university EFL teachers on limited-term contracts. The study looks at factors related to teacher job satisfaction and teacher job dissatisfaction, desired changes to increase job satisfaction and decrease job dissatisfaction, as well as what the future job prospects for limited-term contracted EFL teachers are.

1. Introduction and background

1.1 Japanese higher education context

In 1991 Japan deregulated its higher education system and the effect has been a rapid surge in the number of private universities, which now number 606 out of 782 and account for 73.5% of all university students in Japan (Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology, 2013). This marketization of the higher education has resulted in a more liberal, diversified and individual system (Amano & Poole, 2005). There is also an increased competition to attract students among the shrinking population due to the continually low birth rate figures, resulting in lower profits for private universities (Fraser, 2011). One method used by both private and public institution to reduce their costs to counter act this is to introduce more limited-term contracts for teachers as well as staff (Japan Press Weekly, 2013). This has in turn led to three sub-groups of teachers working in higher education: part-time teachers working at several institutions, full-time teachers on limited-term contracts, and tenured professors.

1.2 The Japanese legal context

The Japanese labour market has gradually moved from offering life-long employment to having a more fluid labour force. In recent years there have been both reactions and counter reactions to

* *School of Cross-Cultural Studies, Sugiyama Jogakuen University*

this development. On April 1, 2013 Japan amended their Labour Contract Act. Before the amendments the total Japanese workforce contained 25% of contracted workers (Okunuki, 2013). In higher education more than 50% of staff, teachers and researchers were employed on contracts (Japan Press Weekly, 2013). Originally these amendments were drawn up in order to improve working conditions for contracted workers by forcing employees to offer permanent jobs after 5 years to workers on limited contracts. Previously such contracts had had the possibility to be renewed indefinitely on an annual basis, but lacked any guarantee of continuation (Nakajima, 2013). The changes in the labour law were meant to offer increased job security but has been claimed to have had the opposite effect by several industry observers (North, 2014; Okunuki, 2014; Rivers, 2013). A 2013 study by Rivers found that all teaching contracts advertised on a popular university recruitment site listed maximum employment periods of 3, 4 or 5 years. Even after an amendment in 2014 to increase the limits to 10 years for positions that involved research duties, there were only a very limited number of full-time contract positions offering longer term-limits than 5 years (Japan Science and Technology Agency, 2015). In addition, some universities have started to limit their part-time teachers to a maximum of 5 years in order not to be forced to offer them permanent employment. There has been a backlash and workers' unions have negotiated reversals of some changes on a local basis but the educational industry as a whole is experiencing a heightened level of uncertainty (General Union, 2016). These new labour rules are predicted to lead to less dedication of teachers contracted to universities (Rivers, 2013), diminished quality and motivation of teachers (Burrows, 2007), deferral of long-term research projects (Japan Press Weekly, 2013), interference with personal long-term plans for workers (Okunuki, 2013), and to a future two-tier society (Brooks, 2015). Concerns are being raised as this trend is continuing both within the educational system and in society in general with internal affairs ministry figures showing that non-regular workers made up 40% of the total workforce in Japan (Osaki, 2015).

2. Literature review

2.1 EFL teacher job satisfaction in higher education in Japan

Job satisfaction has been investigated in a variety of industries. Locke (1976, in Weiss 2002) defined job satisfaction as an enjoyable or positive emotional state stemming from the assessment of one's job. Two studies investigating teacher job satisfaction in higher education in Japan have recently been published (Sugino, 2010; Tsutsumi, 2014). Both studies focused on teacher motivation/demotivation. Sugino (2010) conducted a quantitative investigation into demotivational factors among university language teachers. The study surveyed 97 teachers, among whom 58 were teaching English. The majority (53.6%) of them were teaching at the Defense Academy of Japan. From the questionnaire Sugino found that "of the 37 items, the top seven [demotivating] items included five items related to factors of student attitudes" (p. 223). The remaining two items in the top seven were 'long meeting hours' and 'much paperwork', both which are related to working conditions. The participants in the study consisted of a mixture of tenured (56.7%), full-time faculty (14.4%) and part-time teachers (28.9%).

Tsutsumi (2014) investigated Japanese university EFL teacher motivation in a mainly quantitative study. The study included 12 teachers, five tenured, four full-time lecturers, and three part-time lecturers. Tsutsumi modified a questionnaire developed by Kassabgy, Boraie, and Schmidt (2001) to the local teaching context and constructed an 86-item questionnaire. Two open ended questions were included at the end of the questionnaire to gather some qualitative data. The study's emphasis was on "overall teachers' motivation and values and real lives in the profession" (p. 127). The results showed that although Japanese English teachers tend to mainly be motivated by intrinsic factors such as "autonomy, self-growth, and seeing students' growth" (p. 134), they also "seek job security among many extrinsic factors" (p. 134).

3. Methodology

3.1 Research area

This research set out to find out more about teacher job satisfaction amongst teachers employed on full-time limited-term contracts in higher education in Japan. There were two main areas of interest.

- 1) What are the factors influencing teacher job satisfaction and job dissatisfaction for teachers employed on full-time limited-term contracts in higher education in Japan?
- 2) What changes would teachers employed on full-time limited-term contracts in higher education in Japan like to see to increase job satisfaction and decrease job dissatisfaction?

3.2 Research methodology

An initial questionnaire was sent out to a group of participants followed by a focus group discussing the results and the possible reasons behind the results. The smaller number of participants in the focus group was made up from a subset of the initial group of teachers participating in the questionnaire.

3.3 Research instruments

An open-ended 8-item questionnaire was used for the first stage of data collection. After consent was received, the focus group were presented with some of the initial results of the questionnaire and discussion questions were asked according to a focus group guide.

3.4 Participants

Purposeful sampling was used for this study to be able to get rich information about the subject matter from a limited number of participants (Patton, 2002). Only participants who were employed as English teachers in higher education on limited-term contracts were invited to participate in this study. Twenty-seven teachers were identified and sent a link to take part in an online questionnaire. The questionnaire was completed by 19 out of 27 invited participants. To gain a deeper insight into the reasoning behind the results of the questionnaire, it was followed up with a focus group consisting of a subgroup of the teachers who had replied to the questionnaire. Purposeful sampling

was also used for this stage of the research. Four teachers took part in the focus group part of the study. A summary of the focus group participants can be found in table 1 and table 2.

Table 1 Gender and nationality of focus group participants

	Male	Female	Total
Japanese		1	1
Foreigners	3		3
Total	3	1	4

Table 2 Attributes of focus group participants

Age	Years in higher education in Japan	Years as limited contract teacher	No. of contracts	Highest degree (completed)
50's	0-4	1	1	Doctorate
40's	5-9	5	1	Master's
30's	10-14	4	1	Master's
40's	10-14	8	2	Doctorate

3.5 Data analysis

The answers from the questionnaire were digitalized and imported into Nvivo. In order not to predetermine what factors contributed to teacher job satisfaction I avoided asking participants to choose factors from a set list or to give any examples. This, I believe, led to more thoughtful answers, but had the disadvantage that the style of answers varied quite significantly. In an attempt to compare them, an initial coding and analysis was performed. Some of the initial results were presented to the focus group in order to discover what the reasons for those results might be, and also to probe further into the topic and to discuss what changes to the system that teachers would like to see implemented. The focus group lasted for a total of 84 minutes, and was digitally recorded, transcribed and then coded in Nvivo. Since this study looked at what teachers said rather than how they said it, the transcript was tidied up and punctuation marks were added for readability. A member check was conducted with some of the participants from the focus group to ensure that the transcription had captured the participants' perspectives (Neuman, 2014). The data from both the questionnaire and the focus group were then analysed using a 6-step thematic analysis developed by Braun & Clarke (2006).

4. Results

The answers from the questionnaire are presented followed by the results of the corresponding discussion from the focus group. I have organized the results into four areas: general factors related to teacher job satisfaction and teacher job dissatisfaction, job satisfaction and dissatisfaction in your teaching context, changes teachers would like to see to increase job satisfaction and decrease job dissatisfaction, and future prospects.

4.1 General factors related to teacher job satisfaction and teacher job dissatisfaction

Questions 1 and 2 asked teachers to list, in order of importance, the factors that contribute to job satisfaction and dissatisfaction. I had suggested participants to list at least 5 factors, but some participants had as few as three and others as many as 15. This made it difficult to take into account the ranking given to each answer. To try to give equal weight to each participant, any factors mentioned outside the top 5 were removed. Only categories in which at least two participants had cited when listing the answers to Q1 and Q2 were included. However, if the same category from Q1 and Q2 were given as an answer in Q3 and Q4 by only one participant, they were listed in order to be able to make comparisons between the different questions. In tables 3 and 4 are the answers given to Q1 and Q2.

Table 3 Answers to question 1

Q1 What factors do you think contribute to teacher job satisfaction?	
Salary	11
Student attitudes	10
Good relationships (with colleagues, staff, and supervisors)	9
Autonomy in teaching	7
Support for research	6
Support from institution	5
Working hours/free time/long holidays	5
Job security	5
Good boss	4
Student improvement	4
Positive feedback	2

Table 4 Answers to question 2

Q2 What factors do you think contribute to teacher job dissatisfaction?	
Bad relationships (with colleagues, staff, and supervisors)	11
Poor student attitudes	9
Bad or low salary	8
Too much work/duties	8
Lack of autonomy	7
Job insecurity	6
Bad boss	5
Unsupportive institution	3
Lack of student improvement	2
Lack of research support	1
Negative feedback	1

The factors brought up by the participants that lead to job satisfaction and job dissatisfaction mirrored each other with only minor differences in ranking. Whilst a good salary was mentioned the most frequently, it was usually not ranked as being one of the highest priorities. On the other hand, good student attitude (including motivated students) was often listed as the most or second most important factor leading to teacher job satisfaction; meanwhile, it also had the second highest frequency with 10 out of 19 participants mentioning it. Similarly, poor student attitude (including unmotivated students) was the second most frequent factor listed leading to dissatisfaction amongst the participants.

Bob (all names of the participants in the focus group are pseudonyms) explained why salary was mentioned by most participants in the following way:

'Cause I think it's one of the things you just expect to have to answer when you're talking about satisfaction, that salary just is part of the mix, even though it may or may not be important.

Mike compared the importance of salary and student attitude in the following way:

Well, I notice student attitudes here was mentioned, and that's something that's pretty high on my list as well. I mean, that's not to do so much with your job, per se, and the satisfaction of the pay and your relationship with the institution. That's just the actual work you do because essentially we are teachers and don't have a whole lot of other work outside of the classroom, so for me, if the students have a good attitude, then it really does make a big difference in my actual satisfaction as a teacher.

Bad relationships were the most frequently stated factor leading to job dissatisfaction in the survey. One answer stated it as "No sense of belonging, support or welcome at the workplace". Another as "Being treated unfairly and/or disrespectfully by Administration". In the focus group Steve expanded how relationships affect job satisfaction in the following way:

If I've got good relationships with colleagues, in a sense, I don't really - I expect that. But [...] if I don't trust somebody or if somebody seems malicious, then it's - like, really undermines my satisfaction.

4.2 Factors related to teacher job satisfaction and teacher job dissatisfaction in participants own teaching context

In an attempt to try to discover more specific factors that can lead to job satisfaction and dissatisfaction a pair of similar question to Q1 and Q2 but with the focus on the participants own teaching context were asked. Most participants listed two or three factors, whilst some only stated one. The answers are listed in table 5 and 6.

Table 5 Answers to question 3

Q3 In your teaching context what gives you the most job satisfaction?	
Student improvement	7
Good students	5
Autonomy in teaching	4
Good relationships (with colleagues, staff, and supervisors)	3
Support from institutions	3
Support for research	2
Good boss	1
Salary	1
Working hours/free time	1
Positive feedback	1

Table 6 Answers to question 4

Q4 In your teaching context what causes you the most job dissatisfaction?	
Limited-term contracts	9
Poor student attitude	3
Lack of autonomy	3
Limited or no student progress	2
Poor organization/leadership	2
Too much work	1

Here the factors stated as leading to job satisfaction and those leading to job dissatisfaction are not mirrored. The three most common factors listed as contributing to teacher job satisfaction all relate directly to teaching: student improvements, good students, and autonomy in teaching. Combined those issues were mentioned 16 times while all other issues combined were raised 12 times. In the focus group there were a couple of times when the participants came back to the issue of 'student improvement'. In the focus group Yuka sums it up by saying: "[student] satisfaction, it is equal to the teacher satisfaction". The group agreed student improvement was an important aspect of being a teacher and teacher job satisfaction but that it was difficult to measure student improvement and student satisfaction. Mike said in regards to improvement: "the only thing really tangible is TOEIC scores". Bob suggested using student surveys but Steve pointed out that "[a] student may be successful but unhappy, so it's hard". In the focus group discussions, the issue of student improvement and student satisfaction were also linked to teacher accountability, salary increases and teacher autonomy. Some participants felt they should get a yearly pay rise. Bob stated:

I want a higher salary because I feel like I deserve this salary a normal thing for this to go up, at least to keep up with inflation, and it makes me a little bit upset that it's just, almost everywhere, it's the same

Steve added:

There's no accountability for work - you know, how well people are working. 'Cause we know that there have been people that don't work well and they get the same salary as everybody else. And then they have trouble with them and they're still back the next year

However, when linking teacher accountability to monitoring of teaching results the focus group was divided if this was a positive thing. Bob said:

The problem is that when it's done, it's almost always done like standardized testing. And it's true for both the students and for the teachers, and then we get into sort of, like you say, the American system, and I would rather not deal with that. I'd rather be accountable to myself that I think I'm doing what I need to do and a good job in my class and have less oversight.

The results of what factors teachers stated contributed to their job satisfaction in their teaching context are largely consistent with Tsutsumi's findings (2014). She found that overall job satisfaction was determined by intrinsic factors such as good relationships with students, helping students and seeing students' growth.

When listing factors leading to dissatisfaction, one topic was by far the most frequently cited: limited-term contracts. It was mentioned 3 times as frequent as the next issue, and in fact, all other issues were only mentioned a combined time of 11. This was also the case when teachers stated what they would like to change in order to either increase job satisfaction or decrease job dissatisfaction (see 4.3).

These findings also have some support in Tsutsumi's results. When she looked at negative influences on EFL teacher motivation she found that some non-tenured teachers cited job insecurity and ambiguous position as demotivating influences (Tsutsumi, 2014). Also in Sugino's (2010) results there are some mentions of job insecurity in the open-ended question asked. However, it seems like the question of job security was not asked in the other parts of the questionnaire, and thus whether it was a major factor in teacher demotivation could not be determined in that study. Sugino's finding that various aspects of poor student attitude increased teacher demotivation does seem to concur with it being listed as the second most frequent answer to questions number 4.

4.3 Changes to increase job satisfaction and decrease job dissatisfaction

The answers to questions 6 and 7 gave a clear indication of what changes teachers would like to see implemented to increase their job satisfaction (see table 7) and to decrease their job dissatisfaction (see table 8).

Table 7 Answers to question 6

Q6 If you could change one thing about your job to increase your job satisfaction what would you change? Why?	
No limited-term contracts	12
Increased influence over curriculum	4
Teach fewer classes	1
Improve communication amongst teachers	1
Remember students' names	1

Table 8 Answers to question 7

Q7 If you could change one thing about your job to decrease your job dissatisfaction what would you change? Why?	
No limited-term contracts	7
Increased influence over curriculum	4
Better salary	2
Teach fewer classes	2
More motivated students	1
More support from administration	1
More scheduled professional development	1
Work in only one department	1

Twelve out of 19 participants (63%) in the survey stated that changing the limited-term in their contracts would be the one thing they would like to see happening. In the focus group Bob elaborated:

If we were to think about it in a more - in a larger scale, that's what we want. We want this job with more job security, right.

Mike added: "No contract limit with salary increases at least matching inflation". When pressed on how this could be implemented, suggestions of having some kind of performance review when renewing the contracts were again suggested by the focus group. However, the fear that these would be too subjective were raised by multiple focus group participants. Mike said:

We had regular observations, and I didn't find a lot of value in that because seemed to me like in the situations where I was observed by other teachers or head teachers or supervisors, it's such a subjective thing for them. [...] like, difference in philosophy of just how we approach the environment in the classroom, not saying one is better than the other necessarily. He gets his results, I get my results, but I felt it was such a subjective thing.

Yuka agreed observations could be subjective but still be worthwhile and brought up the suggestion of creating a kind of resume that would also function as a form of annual performance review that

was accessible both internally and externally of the institution. Yuka commented:

You can go outside and show that what your performance was. in that way, we can show our autonomy too, and how we think this is very, very, you know, worthwhile to do it, right, and you know, from the previous work we cited and how we improve it or we suggest at the, you know, improvement for the other things. Because not only [should] we improve our contract, we have to improve the educational system as well, right. So how we change to the better way is kind of that they - if we can have, like, 'educational document', kind of a 'resume' or something like that we can post every year, and then they can judge from that too.

The idea of teachers having some kind of teaching portfolio where they state what they had done in the classroom, the justification for doing so and what the results were seemed to be supported by the other focus group participants. Bob added:

I think a great idea, like maybe marries this is, like, an e-portfolio system would be great where teachers can say, listen, this is what I'm doing, this is why I'm doing it and showcase it in sort of - it could include videos, student work, everything. And then you don't have this, you know, outsider making a judgment. You're saying this is why I'm doing it and this is what the results are, maybe this is what I need to improve. That type of system I would agree with, I think, and that could be used to base on, you know, maybe performance pay or whatever it may be, or funding that you get to do your ideas, but I think that would maybe be kind of a middle ground.

Steve commented "Might be more - yeah, ultimately more valuable. Certainly get a wider view than just one person coming into the classroom".

In a system with a public teaching portfolio, teachers would still retain autonomy over teaching, which was highly valued in the questionnaire, and it could also address the second most sought after change: more influence over curriculum. If teachers kept a portfolio it could add weight to arguments of wanting to change the curriculum of the courses taught. The importance for freedom in curriculum setting is also raised by Tsutsumi (2014) where it is stated as being a major factor to motivate Japanese EFL teachers.

4.4 Future prospects for limited-term contract teachers

In the questionnaire the participants were asked about their future job prospects (see table 9), and in the focus group the issue of how changes to the system could come about was raised.

Table 9 Answers to question 8

Q8 How do you see your future job prospects?	
Uncertain, unsure	8
Good, positive	5
Difficult	3
Will work outside Japan	2
No answer	1

Five participants reported that their prospects were good with some of them reporting that they believed they were likely to gain a tenured job in the near future. However, the majority stated that the future job prospects were either uncertain or difficult.

One questionnaire answer stated:

The EFL teaching marketplace is undergoing some fairly significant changes (overly & covertly). To be honest, I hope I will be gainfully employed at a place that appreciates my efforts in and out of the classroom. However, this might be a case of wishful thinking. Thus, I don't know how I see my job prospects. In eight months, I could be unemployed or underemployed... Hard to say anything with any certainty.

When asked about the future of the contracts in higher education in the focus group Steve stated:

But my suspicion is that the contracts are a symptom of other things that are going on. So - and if you come to the money situation, I think that just - I mean, the demographics of Japan and trying to find students to fill seats, these kinds of issues are really kind of the ones that are overwhelming them.

Bob commented:

And it's not just the universities that you're thinking about, but the wider economy. You know, Japan with a decreasing population and not really doing much about it and universities not having enough students, I mean, is there going to be jobs in five years, so that adds into the job insecurity as well.

When asked if the system could be changed Bob answered:

I don't think it will change willingly. I don't think there's anybody that's sitting there going, like, whoa, we've gotta change this to make it better for the teachers. What I do think could be possible is there could be a big change. Like, say for example, Japan suddenly says listen, we have to bring immigrants into the country in order to increase the population, and they do that, and then you have a lot maybe that could come to university. It might actually bolster our jobs because we're English-speaking faculty members and they might, you know, be more willing to hire us as tenure or something like that.

Steve added about political change:

And you know, you'd hope that there would be a government party that would be doing the job for them, know what I'm saying. Okay, well, we've gotta educate these people that, you know, the future is this other way, but I don't see that happening. [...] It's stuck. Really stuck. And as you say, maybe if they, you know, bring in a lot of people or Japan goes to war with China or something like that, or there's an economic crisis that just blows things outta the water, but I'm not - you know, probably none of those things are gonna happen anytime soon.

Mike summarized in the following way, "Nothing's gonna change unless there's a force that's gonna change it, I think".

The participants' concerns might be justified since there is little indication that the Japanese government are planning to strengthen language education at university level. In 2015, the current government instead seemed to want the Ministry of Education to cut funding to humanities and refocus it on science related programs (Harding, 2015).

5. Conclusions and discussion

The findings from the questionnaire and the focus group confirm some the claims by other researchers in regards to teacher job satisfaction in the Japanese university context (Sugino, 2010; Tsutsumi, 2014). This study supports Tsutsumi's findings that developing a good relationship with students and seeing them improve are key factors leading to high teacher satisfaction. Also, Tsutsumi's conclusion of the importance of teachers having an influence over the curriculum was confirmed. In regards to factors that negatively influence teacher job satisfaction; this study supported some of the findings of Sugino in relation to poor student behavior and attitudes leading to decreased teacher motivation. However, this study has uncovered an increasing sense of uncertainty among teachers on limited-term contracts that was previously only partly indicated in Tsutsumi's research. Whilst teachers gain job satisfaction from seeing student progress, having autonomy in their teaching and developing relationships in the work place, the lack of job security is a major concern that overshadows other aspects. It is becoming clear that fears brought up by previous researchers that teachers are less dedicated to their institutions are materializing (Rivers, 2013), and that job insecurity affects private and family life affects (Okunuki, 2013). A clear majority of teachers would like to see the system changed, with suggestions of introducing some performance evaluation as a basis for gaining renewed employment. However, there are concerns with how such a system would be developed whilst maintaining teacher autonomy. One solution that was proposed was an introduction of a teacher portfolio that could both showcase and justify teaching methods. In reality teachers expressed little hope for such a system to be developed citing both lack of political initiative and resistance from the teaching institutions. Instead an external force such as immigration or drastic social changes were cited as possible catalyzers for change.

5.1 Suggestions

The issue of lack of job security is not only limited to the educational sector and there is no obvious solution. The wider consequences are starting to be noticed and there are some signs that changes will be made with the teachers' union raising the issue (General Union, 2016). However, a strong political will seems lacking in Japan. This study tried to first explore what issues are effecting this particular category of teachers and then challenge the participants in the focus group to problematize the issue and discuss potential solutions. Hopefully such engagement can be the first step in enacting change. By continuing to look into the matter and by highlighting the impacts, awareness of the issue can be raised further to engage more of the stakeholders. Hopefully, this study can contribute to shedding some light on this evolving and complex area and inspire more discussion and further research.

5.2 Limitations and suggestion for further research

The findings and conclusions in this study are limited in their generalizability due to the fact that there were only 19 participants. There were also a limited number of teachers taking part in the focus group and only one focus group was conducted. Therefore, this study might not have given a representative view of the larger population of university English teachers on limited-term contracts in Japan. Further studies including those with more participants and multiple focus groups would be recommended. Finally, maybe the biggest limitation, is the fact that the researcher himself is a contracted teacher and a former colleague of some of the participants. Whilst this could have led to increased trust from the participants, it might also have affected both the responses given as well as the analysis.

References

- Amano, I., & Poole, G. S. (2005). The Japanese university in crisis. *Higher Education*, 50(4), 685-711.
- Boyer, E. L., Altbach, P. G., & Whitelaw, M. J. (1994). *The Academic Profession: an international perspective* (Princeton, Carnegie Foundation for the Advancement of Teaching).
- Braun, V., & Clarke, V. (2006). Using thematic analysis in psychology. *Qualitative Research in Psychology*, 3(2), 77-101.
- Brooks, D. (2015, March 22). University teachers in Japan work under the shadow of a falling ax. *The Japan Times* Retrieved from: http://www.japantimes.co.jp/community/2015/03/22/issues/university-teachers-in-japan-work-under-the-shadow-of-a-falling-ax-2/#.V1_Gc98rLVp
- Burrows, C. (2007). The effect on limited-term contracts on teaching standards at tertiary-level education in Japan EFL. *OnCue Journal*, 1(1), 64-73.
- Evans, L. (1998). Getting the best out of teachers: Morale, motivation and job satisfaction in the primary school. *Education*, 26(1), 26-30.
- Fraser, M. (2011). Exploring the nature and process of professional identity of teachers. EdD thesis, University of Wollongong.
- General Union (2016). *Victory at Doshisha International Academy - More success to follow?* . Retrieved from:

- <http://generalunion.org/Joomla/index.php/education/1436-victory-at-doshisha-international-academy-more-successes-to-follow>
- Harding, R. (2015 September 25) Japan engulfed by row over university humanities studies *Financial Times*. Retrieved from: <http://www.ft.com/cms/s/0/fea7e674-634a-11e5-a28b-50226830d644.html#axzz4AtzITZFI>
- Ho, C. L., & Au, W. T. (2006). Teaching satisfaction scale measuring job satisfaction of teachers. *Educational and Psychological Measurement*, 66(1), 172-185.
- Japan Press Weekly (2013, February 22). Employers move to terminate employment contracts before labor law revised. *Japan Press Weekly*. Retrieved from: <http://www.japan-press.co.jp/s/news/?id=5233>
- Japan and Technology Agency (2015). www.jrecin.jst.go.jp. Accessed 2015-09-09.
- Kassabgy, O., Boraie, D., & Schmidt, R. (2001). Values, rewards, and job satisfaction in ESL/EFL. In Z. Dörnyei & R. Schmidt (Eds.), *Motivation and second language acquisition* (Technical Report #23, pp. 213-237). Honolulu: University of Hawaii, Second Language Teaching and Curriculum Center.
- Lacy, F. J., & Sheehan, B. A. (1997). Job satisfaction among academic staff: an international perspective, *Higher Education*, 34, 305-322.
- Lester, P. E. (1985). Teacher Job Satisfaction K-12. *Illinois School Research and Development*, 22(1), 32-33.
- Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology (2013) *Educational Statistics*. Retrieved from: <http://www.mext.go.jp/english/statistics/index.htm>
- Nakajima, Y. (2013, November 13). Revised Labor Contract Law -Important changes. Minutes from talk given at JALT Tokyo chapter, JALT, Japan
- Neuman, D. (2014). Qualitative research in educational communications and technology: A brief introduction to principles and procedures. *Journal of Computing in Higher Education*, 26(1), 69-86.
- North, S. (2014). Limited Regular Employment and the Reform of Japan's Division of Labor. *The Asia-Pacific Journal*. 12(15), 1-10.
- Okunuki, H. (2013, March 19). Labor law reform raises rather than relieves workers' worries. *The Japan Times*. Retrieved from: <http://www.japantimes.co.jp/community/2013/03/19/how-tos/labor-law-reform-raises-rather-than-relieves-workers-worries/>
- Okunuki, H. (2014, September 24). Job insecurity among Japan's university teachers is a recipe for further decline. *The Japan Times*. Retrieved from: <http://www.japantimes.co.jp/community/2014/09/24/issues/job-insecurity-among-japans-university-teachers-recipe-decline/>
- Osaki, T. (2015, November 13). Ministry seeks to ease child care leave rule. *The Japan Times*, p. 1.
- Oshagbemi, T. (1997) Job satisfaction and dissatisfaction in higher education, *Management and Training*, 39(9), 354-359.
- Pearson, D. A., & Seiler, R. E. (1983). Environmental satisfiers in academics, *Higher Education* 12, 35-47.
- Rivers, D. J. (2013). Labour contract law amendments: Recruitment indicative of change? *The Language Teacher* 37: 1, 68-71.
- Skaalvik, E. M., & Skaalvik, S. (2010). Teacher self-efficacy and teacher burnout: A study of relations. *Teaching and teacher education*, 26(4), 1059-1069.
- Ssesanga, N.A.K. (2001). *Job Satisfaction of University Academics: Perspectives from Uganda*. Unpublished EdD dissertation, University of Bristol.
- Ssesanga, N.A.K., & Garret, R. M. (2005). Job Satisfaction of University Academics: Uganda. *Higher*

Education 50, 33–56.

Sugino, T. (2010). Teacher demotivational factors in the Japanese language teaching context. *Procedia-Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 3, 216–226.

Tsutsumi, R. (2014). Exploring Japanese University EFL Teacher Motivation. *Pan-Pacific Association of Applied Linguistics (PAAL)*, 18(1), 121–143.

Weiss, H. M. (2002). Deconstructing job satisfaction: Separating evaluations, beliefs and affective experiences. *Human resource management review* 12(2), 173–194.